

Palliative Care & Motor Neurone Disease

Aims of today

- To briefly discuss the MND Network
- To explore what MND is?
- To consider the implications of the disease and its impact on the person, their family, carers and professionals.
- Are people with MND disadvantaged?

Objectives

- At the end of this session you will have a greater understanding of the diverse needs of people living with MND.
- You will have a greater awareness of its impact on individuals and you as a professional

Aims of the Network

- 1: Improve the support and coordination of services for people living with MND
- 2: Promote effective integrated working between health, social, research, charity and volunteer sectors
- The network does not...
 - Replace a person's existing care team but works in partnership with them to promote and develop effective service delivery

MND / ALS

- Terminal neurodegenerative disease
- incidence 1 in 50,000 – approx 7000 at any one time.
- Individual lifetime risk is 1 in 400
- Men affected 1.5 times as often as women
- Average age of onset is 60 years old
- In 10 % of people with MND there is a genetic link

▪ (Talbot & Marsden 2008)

Different types of MND

- 85% - Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS)
- 10% - Progressive Muscular Atrophy (PMA)
- 1% - Primary Lateral Sclerosis (PLS)
- Progressive bulbar palsy – tells site of dominant symptoms rather than predicts rate of progression...

■ (Talbot & Marsden 2008)

BRAIN

UMN

**SPINAL
CORD**

LMN

**MUSCLE
PERIPHERAL
SENSATION**

**Primary
Lateral
Sclerosis**

(1%)

**Progressive
Muscular
Atrophy**

(10%)

**Amyotrophic
Lateral
Sclerosis**

(85%)

Individual trajectory

- No one rate of progression
- Some people can have a single region affected for some time before a progressive pattern is observed
- Duration 3 – 5 years from first symptom

- ‘The neurologist told us 5 years and here I am 4 months later and my husband is dead...’
- ‘The neurologist told us 3 years and here I am 5 years later and I am struggling to continue with the demands of caring...’

Diagnosis

- Not always easy – can be a protracted process
- There is not a definitive test
- Most neurodegenerative diseases are characterised by changes at a microscopic level – not sensitive to current scanning techniques

Towards a diagnosis

- Clinical history
- Neurological examination
 - » Looking for changes in motor system
- Blood tests – exclude other issues
 - CPK an enzyme released from damaged muscle
- Neurophysiological tests
 - Nerve conduction studies (Electromyography EMG)
- MRI scanning - exclude
- Lumbar Puncture – rare - exclude

Genetics

- 10% - family history – disease occurring in one or more first degree relatives (parent or sibling)
- 1/5 of people with familial MND carry mutations in SOD1 gene (about 2-3% of all people with MND)
- Can test family members for SOD1 mutations but this would only show in 20% of people who will get FALS

Genetics

- 10% - family history – disease occurring in one or more first degree relatives (parent or sibling)
- 1993: SOD1 2-3% of people with fMND
- 2008: TDP – 43
- 2009: FUS 3-4% of people with fMND
- Can test family members for SOD1 mutations but this would only show in 20% of people who will get fMND

Protective gene – KIFAP3

‘People with two beneficial variants of KIFAP3 lived on average 4 years those with one or no variants lived on average 2 years and 8 months.’

- Prof Al-Chalabi: ‘Treatments can now be directly designed to exploit the effect of this gene variation. The more usual situation is for genetic risk factors for a disease to be identified rather than survival genes’

Main Symptoms

- **Motor disturbances** – mobility changes – self care
- **Respiratory changes**
- **Dysphasia**
- **Dysphagia**
 - Excessive saliva – drooling
 - Weight loss
- Fasciculation; Spasticity; Cramps
- Pain – secondary to weakness / particularly at joints or spasticity

Respiratory

- Gradual reduction in respiratory muscle strength –
 - often reason for shortened life span
- Diaphragm weakness leads to shallow breathing -
 - Signs: frequent waking, lethargy, early morning headaches, sleepiness
- Shortness of breath – the change in muscle strength can make breathing a more conscious movement – anxiety
- Respiratory assessment
- Consider use of NIV
- Cough / sniff machines

Weight loss

- **Changes in bulbar function – swallow**
- **Muscle atrophy**
- **Reduced appetite**
 - Impact can be both Physical and Social
 - Early input from SaLT and dietician
 - May require - PEG's or RIG
 - Issues
 - Careful planning
 - When to start / stop enteral feeding

Excessive oral secretions

- **Thick:** avoid dehydration suck on boiled sweets, pineapple juice contains an enzyme which can break down thick saliva
- **Thin:** Hyoscine patches (drowsy), Amitriptyline,
- **Bot Tox:** salivary glands – requires expert injection
- The pooling of saliva and weakened throat muscles can cause people to worry about choking
- MNDA: Portable suction machines

Cognitive changes

- 2-3% of can develop a form of dementia where language and behaviour are affected.
- 30 - 40 % of people have mild to moderate cognitive changes
 - Planning
 - Decision making
 - Emotional control
 - Some aspects of language
- **BUT – can still be involved in planning their care**
- Understanding – Continuity of staff – Repetition of information – Multiple presentation of information – Be alert to changing awareness

End of life issues common to consider in MND

- We continually need to plan for and be alert to issues of when to pursue / or not / or when to stop
 - Enteral feeding
 - Non invasive ventilation
 - Tracheostomy / invasive ventilation
- Other issues that may arise
 - Assisted suicide

Riluzole

- Only treatment
- Thought to slow motor neurone loss
- Increases survival by approx 3 months
 - Not sure where in the trajectory the 3 months are

Side effects

- Lethargy
- N & V
- Can effect liver enzymes – need regular blood tests

- Multi centre trial
 - “A randomised placebo-controlled trial of Lithium carbonate in Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis” – LiCALS
 - Prof Hanemann – lead
 - Need 22 people
 - Recruitment period 6 months, from January 2019-July 2019
- MNDA DNA Bank

How are people with MND disadvantaged?

- Difficult to get diagnosis – no single test to confirm
- Rare condition – lack of funding – services can be poorly coordinated
- Ignorance - professional and public
- A short duration where it's
- **Relentless, Remorseless and Fatal**
- Have to quickly face issues of disability as well as death
- Only **ONE** treatment
- Cognitive changes only now beginning to be recognised- people with MND can be seen as difficult by professionals
- Impacts on all aspects of living
- More public acceptance of cancer than neuro conditions

29th International Symposium on
ALS/MND

**Abstracts by 15th May
2019**